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Perceived Personality of the Teachers and Its Effect to Classroom Management

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to examine the perception of the respondents on the personality of their teachers and its effect to their classroom management. A descriptive correlational study was utilized as a design to attain the objective of the study. A descriptive and inferential statistics were utilized to statistically quantify the data gathered from the respondents using a structured questionnaire. 21 secondary students who are officially enrolled at Saint Joseph's College of Baggao Inc (SJCBI) for Academic Year 2019-2020 participated on this study. The result showed that the teacher's personality greatly affects classroom management. It is therefore the major recommendation of this study is for the teachers to continually engage themselves to career development and personality enhancement through seminars and trainings.

INTRODUCTION

Most educational writers and public-school officials insist that personality is one of the most important factors in the successful teachers' equipment. Among other things the teacher himself is an important factor in the failure or success of the learner. Although the teachers' activity should not be the center of emphasis in the classroom, yet it should be borne in mind that the Personality of the teacher is an important element in the total teaching situation. As such, it should be favorable to the overall growth of the students.

According to Moreno Rubio (2009), one significant element that contributes to a successful teacher regardless of a profound content knowledge of his or her subject is classroom management skill. It is, thus, obvious that the study of classroom management has become an important aspect of teacher development. It is contended that classroom management could exert influences on the learning environment for students, which, as a result, affects both their academic competencies and emotional development (Kratowchwill, n.d). This can be considered as a rationale for much research into the effect of classroom management on students' academic achievement and students' behavior.

Hence, according to Atkinson, R. C., & Hilgard, E. (2011), personality is defined as the configuration of individual characteristics and ways of behaving which describe an individual's unique adjustment to his environment. It includes all those characteristics of the person that are important in his adjustment and the maintenance of his self-respect. From early childhood, the individual's concept of self is an important factor in guiding both his personality. He acts consistently in terms of the kind of person believes he is. This self is his personality "viewed from within." ALL his experiences with himself in his environment are integrated into it. Personality includes

the self and structure and more.

Personality structure refers to the persistent unique features that give coherence to a personality. Jurczak, I., & Jurczak, E. (2015). A man's personality structure arises through the roles that culture assigns to him and through individual differences. Social scientists use the word "personality" to refer to the individual's value, or effect on others, his life; or his particular pattern of measurable traits. It is determined by all those characteristics and qualities of the individual that act as stimuli for other people-physique, hair color, complexion, mannerisms, friendship and the Like.

According to Hogan (1991), a person personality is a relatively stable precursor of behavior; it underlies an enduring style of thinking, feeling and acting. However, Guthrie et. al (1998) stated that personality can be defined as a predisposition to act or behave in a characteristic fashion in response to one's environment. Based on Pervin *et. al* (2005), personality refers to the characteristics of the person that account for consistent patterns of feeling, thinking and behaving.

Personality is considered as complex interacting traits.

Parks-Leduc, L., Feldman, G., & Bardi, A. (2015) said that traits of the individual are characteristics such mental ability, mechanical aptitude or talent, masculinity, intermission, and sociability. They can be observed and tested objectively or inferred from observable, measurable behavior. In other words, an individual's personality is a composite of his physical appearance, his mental capacity, his emotional behavior, and his attitude towards others particularly the students.

In the book "Comprehensive Classroom Management: Creating Communities of Support and Solving Problems," Jones and Jones (2007) mentioned one more aspect that the teacher managerial strategies affected students, which is students' motivation. However,

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although motivation is an important factor contributing to students' achievement, hardly can studies that thoroughly investigates its relationship with teacher's management practices be found.

This leads the research to conduct this study which is to assess the perception of the personality of the teachers in Saint Joseph's College of Baggao Inc and its effect to classroom management.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used correlational research design. In this method, the researcher tried to elicit the needed information for the study through a questionnaire. The data were presented, interpreted, and analyzed to know the relationship between the study's variables.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were students of Saint Joseph's College of Baggao Incorporated at Baggao Cagayan Valley, Philippines. There were 21 senior high students covered by the study because of sampling technique. The study used convenience sampling to gather the information needed in the study.

Data Gathering Tool

The study used survey questionnaire as its primary data-gathering tool. Part I tries to elicit information from the respondents on their age, sex, civil status and year level. Part II tries to get responses of teacher's personality, scholarship, and classroom management.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher personally hands a written request to the high school principal after the proposal has been approved by the research office of the institution. It was augmented with informal interview of the respondents and actual observation.

Data Analysis

After the retrieval of the questionnaire, elicited data was tabulated, analyzed and interpreted using correlational statistical tools.

RESULT

As revealed in the findings regarding to sex, most of the respondents are female and most of them are single when it comes to civil status.

Table 01 shows that there are 3.10 weighted mean

Table 1: Perceived Personality the Teachers by the Respondents

Variables	Mean	Description
Teachers are neat in appearance	3.10	Strongly Agree
Teachers are strict, but kind, friendly and approachable	2.76	Agree
Teachers are enthusiastic, interesting, stimulating and encouraging	2.62	Agree
Teachers are tolerant, polite and mature in their ways	2.38	Agree
Teachers have sense of humor	2.76	Agree
Overall Mean	2.72	Agree

with description of strongly agree in the perception of respondents that their teachers are neat in appearance. Second, 2.76, 2.62, 2.38 and 2.76 which all fall under agree description were accumulated from the variables Teachers are strict, but kind, friendly and approachable, Teachers are enthusiastic, interesting, stimulating and encouraging, Teachers are tolerant, polite, and mature in their ways, and Teachers have sense of humor,

respectively. It resulted to overall mean of 2.72 weighted mean with agree as description.

As presented in table 02 on the perception of the respondents on the classroom performance of their teachers, it reached an overall mean of 3.38 which has a description of strongly agree. This means that the respondents perceived that their teachers are equipped with the right knowledge and skills to carry out their

Table 2: Perceived Classroom Performance of the Teachers by the Respondents

Variables	Mean	Description
Teachers know their subject very well.	3.86	Strongly Agree
Teachers are progressive- always studying the learning.	3.48	Strongly Agree
Teachers are interested in their work and in their profession.	3.14	Strongly Agree
Teachers conduct the class in an informal easy, natural way, giving their students enough time to think and freedom to express themselves.	3.14	Strongly Agree
Teachers begin and dismiss their class on time	3.75	Strongly Agree
Teachers use different methods and techniques of teaching adjusting them to physical and mental growth of the students.	3.38	Strongly Agree
Teachers make review or drill work a part of their daily teaching procedure.	3.71	Strongly Agree
Teachers use many instructional devices or illustrations to supplement the method used.	3.24	Strongly Agree
Teachers adjust the activities to the learning capacities, interest, and comprehension of their students.	3.19	Strongly Agree
Teachers give clear and varies assignments.	3.48	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.38	Strongly Agree

Table 3: Perceived Classroom Management of the Teachers by the Respondents

Variables	Mean	Description
Teachers' set-up definite aims to be accomplished and organizes their subject matter.	3.43	Strongly Agree
Teachers are always prepared for their class.	3.29	Strongly Agree
Overall mean	3.36	Strongly Agree

job. Meanwhile, all the variables reflected got more than weighted mean of 3 which ended with strongly agree description.

Table 03 illustrates that the respondents perceived that their teachers are always ready to their class with a weighted mean of 3.39 or strongly agree and the highest is that the respondents perceived that their teacher's set-up definite aims to be accomplished and organizes their subject matter with weighted mean of 3.43 or strongly agree.

DISCUSSION

The students rated themselves on the physical and mental qualities as favorable. This shows good sign of quality teacher's process. They also rated themselves favorable in their occupational attitude and personal character. Bernardo, A. B. I. (2003), discussed that mental and basic abilities must be reinforced in classroom for the students to be life-long learners. Generally, the teachers exhibited favorable character and desirable practices that may bring about positive behavior among the students. Classroom management is a key responsibility for every classroom teacher. Teachers' abilities to manage classrooms can influence their self-efficacy and student success rates. In order for teachers to teach effectively, they must possess an understanding of how to create and maintain a classroom environment that is conducive to learning. Brown and Inglis (2013) believed that improving teaching efficacy and practice would require ongoing professional development. Teachers who understand the connections between their self-efficacy and student success rates, can promote student achievement through their daily efforts. The study also shows that the teachers have adequate classroom management skills, which ensures pleasurable teaching learning situation. This revelation was clearly presented in the over-all average findings. This apparently means that teacher's characteristics and behavior patterns relate to how they manage their class.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher concluded that the teacher's personality greatly affects classroom management. Classroom management is essential to learning and in order to achieve learning goals, teachers must be proficient at organizing and managing their classrooms (Ediger, M., 2013). It is therefore the major recommendation of this study is for the teachers to continually engage themselves to career development and personality enhancement through seminars and trainings.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study correlational examined the effects of teachers' personality to classroom management, the following are recommended:

1. For the teachers to continually engage themselves to career development and personality enhancement through seminars and trainings.
2. For the school to reinforce faculty training needs that would empower them to be more productive and efficient.

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